

**ON THE STRUCTURE OF SETS WITH
SMALL DOUBLING PROPERTY ON THE PLANE (II)**

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Abstract

Let $\mathbb{K} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^2$ be a finite set of lattice points in the plane \mathbb{R}^2 . Assume that $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| < (4 - \frac{2}{s+1})|\mathbb{K}| - (2s + 1)$. If $|\mathbb{K}|$ is sufficiently large, then there exist s parallel lines which cover \mathbb{K} . Moreover, if $s \geq 19$, then there is a parallelogram \mathcal{P} in the plane \mathbb{R}^2 such that $|\mathcal{P} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2| \leq 24(|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| - 2|\mathbb{K}| + 1)$ and the set \mathbb{K} is Freiman-isomorphic to a subset of $\mathcal{P} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2$.

– Dedicated to Prof. Melvyn Nathanson on the occasion of his 60th birthday

1. Introduction and Main Result.

An *inverse problem of additive number theory* consists in deducing the structure of a set M from the behavior of the *sumset* $2M = M + M = \{x + y : x, y \in M\}$. Assume that $|2M|$ is small compared to $|M|$. What information does this give about the set M ? If $|2M| = 2|M| - 1$, then M is an arithmetic progression. If we choose bigger values for $|2M|$ the problem ceases to be trivial. Freiman’s Main Theorem (see [F1,F2], [DLY] and [Na] for further references) gives information about the structure of finite sets $M \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$ having *small doubling property*: if $|M + M| < \sigma|M|$, then M is contained in a proper d -dimensional arithmetic progression $\mathcal{P} = \{a + x_1g_1 + \dots + x_dg_d : 0 \leq x_i < \ell_i\}$, where $d \leq [\sigma - 1]$ and $\ell(\mathcal{P}) = |\mathcal{P}| \leq c(\sigma)|M|$. In applications it is important to have an effective version of Freiman’s theorem. Building on earlier ideas of Ruzsa [Ru] and Bilu [Bi], Chang [Ch] recently obtained the best bound so far: her argument implies the estimate $c(\sigma) \leq \exp(C\sigma^2 \log^3 \sigma)$, for an absolute constant $C > 0$. However, in the case of small values of the *doubling coefficient* $\sigma = \frac{|2\mathbb{K}|}{|\mathbb{K}|}$, elementary methods yield sharper results. More precisely, we have

Theorem A. *Let \mathbb{K} be a finite set of \mathbb{Z}^2 of cardinality $k = |\mathbb{K}|$.*

- (i) *If $|2\mathbb{K}| < 3k - 3$, then \mathbb{K} is contained in an arithmetic progression of no more than $v = |2\mathbb{K}| - k + 1$ terms.*

- (ii) If $|2\mathbb{K}| < \frac{10}{3}k - 5$ and $k \geq 11$, then either \mathbb{K} is contained in a line or \mathbb{K} is included in two parallel arithmetic progressions with the same common difference having together no more than $v = |2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + 3$ terms.
- (iii) If $|2\mathbb{K}| < 3.5k - 7$ and $k \geq 1344$, then either \mathbb{K} is contained in two parallel lines or \mathbb{K} is included in three compatible arithmetic progressions with the same common difference having together no more than $v = \frac{3}{4}(|2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + 5)$ terms.

The proofs of (i) and (ii) can be found in [F1], pp. 11 and 28; (iii) was obtained in [S2].

The present paper is devoted to the generalization of these theorems to the general case $s \geq 4$. We shall now consider a finite set \mathbb{K} of lattice points on a plane having the *small doubling property* $|2\mathbb{K}| < (4 - \frac{2}{s+1})|\mathbb{K}| - (2s + 1)$. We wish to obtain a reasonable estimate for the number of lattice points of a "minimal" parallelogram that covers the set \mathbb{K} ; more precisely, if \mathcal{L} is a lattice generated by \mathbb{K} , we are interested in precise upper bounds for the number of points of \mathcal{L} that lie in the convex hull of \mathbb{K} . Our main result asserts that \mathbb{K} is located inside a parallelogram that lies on a few lines which are well filled:

Theorem 1. *Let $s \geq 19$ be an integer and let \mathbb{K} be a finite subset of \mathbb{Z}^2 such that*

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| < (4 - \frac{2}{s+1})|\mathbb{K}| - (2s + 1). \tag{1.1}$$

- (a) *If $|\mathbb{K}| \geq 16s(s+1)(2s+1)$, then there exist s parallel lines which cover the set \mathbb{K} .*
- (b) *If \mathbb{K} lies on exactly s parallel lines, then there is a lattice $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^2$ and a parallelogram \mathcal{P} such that $|\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{L}| \leq 24(|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| - 2|\mathbb{K}| + 1)$ and $\mathbb{K} \subseteq (\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{L}) + v$, for some $v \in \mathbb{Z}^2$.*

This gives an accurate description for the structure of planar sets having doubling coefficient $\sigma < 4$: the set \mathbb{K} can be covered by s parallel lines (the best possible result). Moreover, a suitable affine isomorphism maps \mathbb{K} into a set of lattice points that lies inside a parallelogram of bounded area. This assertion provides an answer to Freiman's question [F4, section 7]. The reader will notice that Chang's quantitative estimate $c(\sigma) \leq \exp(C\sigma^2 \log^3 \sigma)$ is extremely weak when compared to the new upper bound

$$|\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{L}| \leq 24(|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| - 2|\mathbb{K}| + 1), \tag{1.2}$$

implied by Theorem 1(b). This estimate is nearly sharp and it is far better than the bounds arising from the known proofs of Freiman's theorem. Nevertheless, we believe that for a best possible result, the constant factor 24 should be replaced by $\frac{1}{2}(1 + \frac{1}{s-1})$, if instead of a covering parallelogram \mathcal{P} we consider the convex hull of \mathbb{K} . We suggest the following.

Conjecture S. Let \mathbb{K} be a finite subset of \mathbb{Z}^2 that lies on exactly $s \geq 2$ parallel lines. If

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| < \max \left\{ 4|\mathbb{K}| - 6, \left(5 - \frac{2}{s-1}\right)(|\mathbb{K}| - 1) - 2s + 4 \right\}, \tag{1.3}$$

then the convex hull of \mathbb{K} can be covered by $2s - 2$ compatible arithmetic progressions having together no more than

$$v = \frac{s}{2(s-1)} (|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| - 2|\mathbb{K}| + 2s - 1) \text{ terms.} \tag{1.4}$$

So far inequality (1.4) has been proved only for $s = 2$ (see [S1], pp. 128) and $s = 3$ (see Theorem A (iii)).

The remaining sections are arranged as follows. Examples 1, 2 and 3 of Section 2, show that if Conjecture S is true, then this is the best possible result. Assertion (a) of Theorem 1 follows from [S1], Theorem A. Assertion (b) is the heart of this work; its proof consists of two distinct parts. In Section 3 we show that \mathbb{K} is contained in $2s - 2$ equidistant parallel arithmetic progressions, while we postpone to Section 6 the proof of inequality (1.2). Section 4 deals with addition of distinct sets of integers and provides an important lower bound for $|2\mathbb{K}|$. In Section 5 we prepare for the proof of Theorem 1(b) by showing that we may cover the set \mathbb{K} by s short intervals. We conclude the proof in Section 6.

2. Notation, Preliminaries, and Examples.

As usual, \mathbb{Z} denotes the rational integers and \mathbb{N} the nonnegative elements of \mathbb{Z} . If A is a finite set, the number of its elements will be denoted by $|A| = a$. We denote by $A + B$ the algebraic sum of two finite sets; $2A = A + A$ is called the sum set of A . If $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k\} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$ with $k \geq 2$, we denote by $d(A)$ the g.c.d. $(a_2 - a_1, a_3 - a_1, \dots, a_k - a_1)$; if $k = 1$, we put $d(A) = 0$. By the length $l(A)$ of a set A we mean the difference, $l(A) = \max(A) - \min(A)$, between its maximal and minimal elements. Let \mathbb{R}^2 be a two dimensional Euclidean plane and \mathbb{Z}^2 the additive group of integral vectors in \mathbb{R}^2 . A vector will be denoted in the form $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2)$, where v_1, v_2 are the coordinates of the vector with respect to the basis $\{\mathbf{e}_1 = (1, 0), \mathbf{e}_2 = (0, 1)\}$. A lattice in \mathbb{R}^2 is an abelian group \mathcal{L} generated by a set of two linearly independent vectors. We shall use a generalization of Theorem A(i) in the case of distinct summands. This result, obtained by Freiman in [F3], was sharpened in [LS] and [S3].

Theorem B. Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ and $B \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be finite sets such that $0 \in A \cap B$ and $d(A \cup B) = 1$.

(i) If $\max(l(A), l(B)) \geq |A| + |B| - 2$, then $|A + B| \geq |A| + |B| - 3 + \min(|A|, |B|)$.

(ii) If $d(A) > 1$, then $|A + B| \geq |B| + 2|A| - 2$.

Let us now fix the notation for the following sections. Let \mathbb{K} be a finite set included in \mathbb{Z}^2 having the small doubling property (1.1). By Theorems A(ii) and A(iii), we may assume that \mathbb{K} lies on exactly $s \geq 4$ parallel lines; we shall also assume that \mathbb{K} contains the origin which does not affect the generality; $|2\mathbb{K}|$ is invariant under *Freiman isomorphisms* ([F1], p. 2). Thus, after a coordinate change, we may write

$$\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{K}_1 \cup \mathbb{K}_2 \cup \dots \cup \mathbb{K}_s,$$

where the set \mathbb{K}_i lies on the line $(x = x_i)$ and $0 = x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_s$. Let $K_i \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$ be the set of ordinates of $\mathbb{K}_i = \mathbb{K} \cap (x = x_i)$; let $k_i = |\mathbb{K}_i|$, $d_i = d(K_i)$, $m_i = \min(K_i)$, $M_i = \max(K_i)$, and $\mathbf{P}_i = (x_i, m_i)$, for every $1 \leq i \leq s$. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s\}$. It is clear that we may assume $\mathbf{P}_1 = (0, 0)$. Put $k = |\mathbb{K}|$, $k_{\max} = \max\{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_s\}$ and $d = d(\mathbb{K}) = \gcd(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_s)$. *Everywhere in this paper, we denote by \mathbb{K} a set defined as above, unless the contrary is stated explicitly.* We will use the following three inequalities (see [F1, p. 25])

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq 4k - (k_1 + k_s) - 2s + 1, \tag{2.1}$$

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq 2k + (k_1 + k_s)(s - 1) - 2s + 1, \tag{2.2}$$

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq \left(4 - \frac{2}{s}\right)k - 2s + 1. \tag{2.3}$$

In the remainder of Section 2 we obtain an estimate for k_{\max} (see Lemma 1) and we provide three examples which explain the bounds (1.3) and (1.4) (see Examples 1, 2 and 3 below).

Lemma 1.

(i) $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq 2k + (s - 1)k_t + (t - 1)k_1 + (s - t)k_s - (2s - 1)$, for every $1 \leq t \leq s$.

(ii) $k_{\max} \leq \frac{1}{s-1}(|2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + 1) + 1 = \frac{1}{s-1}(|2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + s)$.

Proof. Note that $2x_1 < x_1 + x_i < x_1 + x_{t-1} < x_t + x_j < x_{t+1} + x_s < x_\ell + x_s < 2x_s$, for $1 \leq i \leq t-1$, $1 \leq j \leq s$ and $t + 1 \leq \ell \leq s$. We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| &\geq \sum_{1 \leq i \leq t-1} |K_1 + K_i| + \sum_{1 \leq j \leq s} |K_t + K_j| + \sum_{t+1 \leq \ell \leq s} |K_\ell + K_s| \\ &\geq \sum_{1 \leq i \leq t-1} (k_1 + k_i - 1) + \sum_{1 \leq j \leq s} (k_t + k_j - 1) + \sum_{t+1 \leq \ell \leq s} (k_\ell + k_s - 1) \\ &= 2k + (s - 1)k_t + (t - 1)k_1 + (s - t)k_s - (2s - 1). \end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

Inequality (i), which generalizes (2.2), is now proved. Using (2.4) and $k_1 \geq 1, k_s \geq 1$, we get that $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 2k + (s - 1)k_t - s$, for every $1 \leq t \leq s$. Lemma 1 is proved. \square

We will show that the upper bound (1.3) of Conjecture S cannot be further relaxed. To this end, we need the following result, which will also be used in Lemma 6 of Section 5.

Lemma 2. *Let $d = d(\mathbb{K})$. Assume that there exists a vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ such that the sets $\mathbb{K}_1, \mathbb{K}_2, \dots, \mathbb{K}_{s-1}$ are included in the lattice $\mathcal{L} = \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{v} + \mathbb{Z}d\mathbf{e}_2 = \{x\mathbf{v} + y(0, d) : x, y \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. If \mathbb{K}_s is not included in \mathcal{L} , then $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq (5 - \frac{2}{s-1})(k-1) - 2s + 4$ and $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - (k_1 + k_s) - k_{s-1} - 2s$.*

Proof. Using d divides d_s and hypothesis $\mathbb{K}_s \not\subseteq \mathcal{L}$, we see that $\mathbb{K}_s \cap \mathcal{L} = \emptyset$. Put $\mathbb{K}^* = \mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{K}_s$. Note that $(\mathbb{K}_s + \mathbb{K}^*) \cap \mathcal{L} = \emptyset$. Indeed, if a vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathcal{L}$ can be written as a sum $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_s + \mathbf{v}_i$, with $\mathbf{v}_s \in \mathbb{K}_s, \mathbf{v}_i \in \mathbb{K}_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq s-1$, then $\mathbf{v}_s \in \mathcal{L} - \mathbb{K}_i \subseteq \mathcal{L} - \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$, which contradicts $\mathbb{K}_s \cap \mathcal{L} = \emptyset$. Moreover, we clearly have $2\mathbb{K}^* \subseteq \mathcal{L} + \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$. We deduce that $2\mathbb{K}^* \cap (\mathbb{K}_s + \mathbb{K}^*) = \emptyset$ and thus

$$\begin{aligned} |2\mathbb{K}| &\geq |2\mathbb{K}^*| + |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}_s| + |2\mathbb{K}_s| = |2\mathbb{K}^*| + \sum_{1 \leq j \leq s-1} |\mathbb{K}_j + \mathbb{K}_s| + |2\mathbb{K}_s| \\ &\geq |2\mathbb{K}^*| + \sum_{1 \leq j \leq s-1} (k_j + k_s - 1) + (2k_s - 1) = |2\mathbb{K}^*| + k + s(k_s - 1). \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

\mathbb{K}^* lies on $s-1 \geq 2$ parallel lines and we shall estimate $|2\mathbb{K}^*|$ by using inequalities (2.1) and (2.3). Using (2.3), we get $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq ((4 - \frac{2}{s-1})|\mathbb{K}^*| - 2(s-1) + 1) + k + s(k_s - 1)$ and so

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq (5 - \frac{2}{s-1})(k-1) - 2s + 4 + (s-4 + \frac{2}{s-1})(k_s - 1) \geq (5 - \frac{2}{s-1})(k-1) - 2s + 4. \tag{2.6}$$

Using (2.1) instead of (2.3), we obtain from (2.5) that

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq \left(4|\mathbb{K}^*| - (k_1 + k_{s-1}) - 2(s-1) + 1\right) + k + s(k_s - 1) \geq 5k - (k_1 + k_s) - k_{s-1} - 2s. \tag{2.7}$$

With this observation, the proof of Lemma 2 is complete. □

We shall now explain the upper bound (1.3) and show that inequality (2.6) is best possible.

Example 1. Let $s \geq 3, d \geq 2, n \geq 2$ be positive integers. The set $A \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^2$ defined by

$$A = \{(x, dy) : 0 \leq x \leq s-2, 0 \leq y \leq n-1\} \cup \{(s-1, 1)\},$$

lies on s parallel lines and satisfies the assumptions of Lemma 2. It is easy to verify that $|A| = (s-1)n + 1$ and $|2A| = (5 - \frac{2}{s-1})(|A| - 1) - 2s + 4$. Moreover, if \mathcal{P} is a covering parallelogram of A , then an estimate $|\mathcal{P} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2| = O(|A|)$ cannot hold, because $d = d(A)$ can be any sufficiently large integer. Thus, Conjecture S cannot be sharpened by increasing the upper bound (1.3). The same conclusion follows by examining the set B defined in Example 2 below. Note that, in contrast to Example 1, the set B satisfies $d(B) = 1$.

Example 2. Let $s \geq 3, t, n \geq 2$ be integers, such that $t \geq 2n - 1$. The set

$$B = \{(x, y) : 0 \leq x \leq s-2, 0 \leq y \leq n-1\} \cup \{(s-1, t)\} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^2,$$

lies on s parallel lines. We have $|B| = (s-1)n + 1$ and $|2B| = (5 - \frac{2}{s-1})(|B| - 1) - 2s + 4$. Clearly, an upper bound of the form $|\mathcal{P} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2| = O(|B|)$ cannot hold, because t can be any sufficiently large integer.

We conclude Section 2 by showing that the upper bound (1.4) is tight.

Example 3. Let $s \geq 3, h, b \geq 2$ be positive integers and assume $2h < b$. Let us define

$$\mathbb{L}^* = \{(x, y) : 0 \leq x \leq s - 1, 0 \leq y \leq bx\} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{L} = \mathbb{L}^* \setminus \{(x, y) : bx - h < y < bx\}.$$

\mathbb{L}^* is the convex hull of \mathbb{L} and it is not difficult to show that

$$2\mathbb{L}^* = \{(x, y) : 0 \leq x \leq 2s - 2, 0 \leq y \leq bx\} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2 \quad \text{and} \quad 2\mathbb{L} = 2\mathbb{L}^* \setminus \{(x, y) : bx - h < y < bx\}.$$

Therefore, if $H^* = |\mathbb{L}^*| - |\mathbb{L}| = (s - 1)(h - 1)$, then $|2\mathbb{L}| = |2\mathbb{L}^*| - (2s - 2)(h - 1) = |2\mathbb{L}^*| - 2H^* = (4 - \frac{2}{s})|\mathbb{L}^*| - 2s + 1 - 2H^*$ and thus $|2\mathbb{L}| = (4 - \frac{2}{s})|\mathbb{L}| - 2s + 1 + (2 - \frac{2}{s})H^*$. If h is small enough, then the set \mathbb{L} satisfies the small doubling hypothesis (1.1) and the convex hull of \mathbb{L} consists on s parallel arithmetic progressions having together exactly $v = |\mathbb{L}^*| = |\mathbb{L}| + H^* = |\mathbb{L}| + \frac{s}{2(s-1)}(|2\mathbb{L}| - (4 - \frac{2}{s})|\mathbb{L}| + 2s - 1)$ terms. This shows that the upper bound (1.4) is sharp.

3. The Set \mathbb{K} Lies Between the Lines $(x = 0)$ and $(x = 2s - 3)$.

In this section we will prove that the small doubling property (1.1) or *even* inequality (6.1) imply the upper bound $l(X) = x_s - x_1 \leq (2|X| - 3)d(X)$, for the length $l(X)$ of X . This means that \mathbb{K} is included in $2s - 2$ equidistant parallel arithmetic progressions. Let us put

$$\varepsilon = \frac{2 - \sqrt{3}}{\sqrt{3}}. \tag{3.1}$$

First, we prove

Proposition 1. *Let $\mathbb{K} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^2$ be a finite set that lies on $s \geq 3$ parallel lines. If $d(X) = 1$ and $l(X) \geq 2|X| - 2$, then $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq \left(4 + \varepsilon - \frac{4(1+\varepsilon)}{s+1}\right)|\mathbb{K}| - 2s + 3$.*

Proof. We project the set \mathbb{K} onto the line $(y = 0)$. We recall the definition from Freiman [F1, page 27] for the particular case of a set of lattice points. For some fixed x , let r be the number of points in \mathbb{K} having the first coordinate x , i.e., r points of the form $(x, y_1), (x, y_2), \dots, (x, y_r)$. Instead of these r points we choose the points $(x, 0), (x, 1), \dots, (x, r - 1)$. This process is performed for all fixed x , with $r \geq 1$. The set \mathbb{A} so obtained is called the projection of the set \mathbb{K} onto the line $(y = 0)$. Theorem 1.16 [F1] states that

$$|\mathbb{A}| = |\mathbb{K}| \quad \text{and} \quad |\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \leq |\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}|. \tag{3.2}$$

The projection \mathbb{A} is decomposable into

$$t = k_{\max} = \max\{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_s\} \geq \frac{|\mathbb{K}|}{s} \tag{3.3}$$

subsets $\mathbb{A}_1, \mathbb{A}_2, \dots, \mathbb{A}_t$ which lie on t parallel lines $(y = 0), (y = 1), \dots, (y = t - 1)$. Let the set of abscissae for $(y = j - 1)$ be equal to A_j and denote the length of A_j by $l(A_j)$. It is clear that $X = A_1 \supseteq A_2 \supseteq A_3 \supseteq \dots \supseteq A_t$ and therefore:

$$(i) \quad l(A_1) = l(X) \geq 2|X| - 2 = 2|A_1| - 2 \text{ and } d(A_1) = d(X) = 1; \tag{3.4}$$

$$(ii) \quad |A_i| \leq |A_1| \text{ and } l(A_i) \leq l(A_1), \text{ for every } 1 \leq i \leq t.$$

We estimate $|\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}|$ using the second assertion of Proposition 2 below. In view of (3.2) and (3.3) we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| &\geq |\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \geq (4 + \varepsilon - \frac{2}{t})|\mathbb{A}| - 4t + 1 = (4 + \varepsilon)|\mathbb{A}| - \frac{2}{k_{\max}}|\mathbb{A}| - 4k_{\max} + 1 \\ &= (4 + \varepsilon)|\mathbb{K}| - \frac{2}{k_{\max}}|\mathbb{K}| - 4k_{\max} + 1 \geq (4 + \varepsilon)|\mathbb{K}| - 4k_{\max} - 2s + 1. \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

Moreover, using the first assertion of Proposition 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| &\geq |\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \geq 3|\mathbb{A}| + (t - 1)(|A_1| + |A_t|) - 4t + 1 \\ &= 3|\mathbb{K}| + (k_{\max} - 1)(|A_1| + |A_t|) - 4k_{\max} + 1 \geq 3|\mathbb{K}| + (k_{\max} - 1)(s + 1) - 4k_{\max} + 1 \\ &= 3|\mathbb{K}| + (s - 3)k_{\max} - s. \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

Multiplying inequality (3.5) by $s - 3$ and adding it to inequality (3.6) multiplied by 4 we get $(s + 1)|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq ((4 + \varepsilon)(s + 1) - (4 + 4\varepsilon))|\mathbb{K}| - (2s^2 - 3s + 3)$. This readily implies the assertion of Proposition 1. \square

It remains to prove the following auxiliary result which seems to be of some independent interest.

Proposition 2. *Let $\mathbb{A} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^2$ be a finite set which lies on t parallel lines $(y = y_u), 1 \leq u \leq t$, with $y_1 < \dots < y_t$. Let A_u be the set of abscissae for $(y = y_u)$ and assume that*

$$(i) \quad d(A_1) = 1 \text{ and } l(A_1) \geq 2|A_1| - 2,$$

$$(ii) \quad l(A_u) \leq l(A_1) \text{ and } |A_u| \leq |A_1|, \text{ for every } 1 \leq u \leq t.$$

Then, $|\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \geq 3|\mathbb{A}| + (t - 1)(|A_1| + |A_t|) - 4t + 1$ and $|\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \geq (4 + \varepsilon - \frac{2}{t})|\mathbb{A}| - 4t + 1$.

Proof. Put $a = |\mathbb{A}|$ and $a_u = |A_u|$ for every $1 \leq u \leq t$. In order to estimate $|2\mathbb{A}|$, we shall use the lower bound $|A_1 + A_u| \geq |A_1| + 2|A_u| - 3, 1 \leq u \leq t$; this is true in view of Theorem B(i). We claim that if we choose $j_0, 1 \leq j_0 \leq t$ such that

$$a_i \leq a_{j_0}, \text{ for every index } i \geq j_0, \tag{3.7}$$

then

$$|\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \geq 3|\mathbb{A}| + (j_0 - 1)(a_1 + a_{j_0}) - 4t + 1. \tag{3.8}$$

We prove inequality (3.8). For every j , $1 \leq j \leq t$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| &\geq \sum_{1 \leq u \leq j} |A_1 + A_u| + \sum_{2 \leq u \leq t} |A_j + A_u| + \sum_{j < u \leq t} |A_t + A_u| \\ &\geq \sum_{1 \leq u \leq j} (a_1 + 2a_u - 3) + \sum_{2 \leq u \leq t} (a_j + a_u - 1) + \sum_{j < u \leq t} (a_t + a_u - 1) \\ &= 3|\mathbb{A}| + (j - 1)(a_1 + a_j) + \left[(t - j)a_j - \sum_{j < u \leq t} a_u \right] + (t - j)(a_t + 2) - 4t + 1. \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

But $(t - j_0)a_{j_0} \geq \sum_{j_0 < u \leq t} a_u$, in view of (3.7). Therefore, for $j = j_0$, inequality (3.9) implies the desired lower bound for $|\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}|$. Moreover, for $j_0 = t$ we get from (3.8) that

$$|\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \geq 3|\mathbb{A}| + (t - 1)(a_1 + a_t) - 4t + 1. \tag{3.10}$$

The second assertion of Proposition 2 remains to be proven. We shall use inequalities (3.8) and (3.10). We distinguish two cases.

Case 1. If $|a_1| \geq (1 + \varepsilon)\frac{|\mathbb{A}|}{t}$, then by inequality (3.10) and definition (3.1) we get

$$|\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| \geq 3|\mathbb{A}| + (t - 1)\left((1 + \varepsilon)\frac{a}{t} + 1\right) - 4t + 1 \geq (4 + \varepsilon - \frac{1 + \varepsilon}{t})a - 3t \geq (4 + \varepsilon - \frac{2}{t})a - 3t$$

and Proposition 2 is proved.

Case 2. Assume that $a_1 \leq (1 + \varepsilon)\frac{|\mathbb{A}|}{t}$; define $j_0 = \max\{i : 1 \leq i \leq t, a_i \geq \rho\frac{a}{t}\}$, where $\rho = \frac{1 + \varepsilon}{2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$, by (3.1). Note that the index j_0 is well defined, in view of $a_1 \geq \frac{a}{t} \geq \rho\frac{a}{t}$. Moreover, $a_{j_0} \geq \rho\frac{a}{t}$ and for $i > j_0$ we have $a_i < \rho\frac{a}{t}$; thus (3.7) is true. We claim that

$$j_0 > \frac{1 - \rho}{(1 + \varepsilon) - \rho}t. \tag{3.11}$$

Indeed, we may write $a = |\mathbb{A}| = \sum_{1 \leq u \leq j_0} a_u + \sum_{j_0 < u \leq t} a_u < \sum_{1 \leq u \leq j_0} a_u + (t - j_0)\rho\frac{a}{t}$ and thus $a < j_0a_1 + \rho a - j_0\rho\frac{a}{t} \leq j_0(1 + \varepsilon)\frac{a}{t} + \rho a - j_0\rho\frac{a}{t} = j_0(1 + \varepsilon - \rho)\frac{a}{t} + \rho a$. Thus, $1 < j_0(1 + \varepsilon - \rho)\frac{1}{t} + \rho$ and this implies (3.11), because $1 + \varepsilon - \rho > 0$. We complete the proof by using (3.8) for j_0 defined above. An elementary computation gives

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{A} + \mathbb{A}| &\geq 3|\mathbb{A}| + (j_0 - 1)(a_1 + a_{j_0}) - 4t + 1 > 3a + \left(\frac{1 - \rho}{1 + \varepsilon - \rho}t - 1\right)(a_1 + a_{j_0}) - 4t + 1 \\ &\geq 3a + \left(\frac{1 - \rho}{1 + \varepsilon - \rho}t - 1\right)\left(\frac{a}{t} + \rho\frac{a}{t}\right) - 4t + 1 = 3a + \frac{1 - \rho^2}{1 + \varepsilon - \rho}a - (1 + \rho)\frac{a}{t} - 4t + 1 \\ &= (4 + \varepsilon - \frac{1 + \rho}{t})a - 4t + 1 \geq (4 + \varepsilon - \frac{2}{t})a - 4t + 1. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Using Proposition 1 and the linear isomorphism $(v_1, v_2) \rightarrow (\frac{v_1}{d(X)}, v_2)$ we obtain

Corollary 1. *If $|2\mathbb{K}| < \left(4 + \varepsilon - \frac{4(1 + \varepsilon)}{s + 1}\right)|\mathbb{K}| - 2s + 3$, then $l(X) \leq (2|X| - 3)d(X)$.*

4. On Addition of Two Distinct Sets of Integers and a Lower Bound for $|2\mathbb{K}|$.

In this section we state and prove Lemma 3; inequality (4.1) will be used in Corollary 2 of Section 5, where we show that the set \mathbb{K} can be covered by s short intervals. Define

$$J = J(\mathbb{K}) = \{i \mid 1 \leq i \leq s, d_i = d(\mathbb{K}), M_i - m_i \leq (2k_i - 3)d(\mathbb{K})\} \cup \{i \mid 1 \leq i \leq s; k_i = 1\},$$

and let us denote:

$$\overline{\mathbb{K}} = \bigcup_{i \in J} \mathbb{K}_i, \quad N = |\overline{\mathbb{K}}|.$$

Lemma 3.

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - N - (k_1 + k_s) - 4s = \left(4k_1 + 5k_2 + \dots + 5k_{s-1} + 4k_s\right) - N - 4s. \tag{4.1}$$

Proof. If $J = \{1, 2, \dots, s\}$, then $N = k$ and Lemma 3 clearly follows from (2.1). We suppose that $J \neq \{1, 2, \dots, s\}$ and the proof goes by induction with respect to $s \geq 2$.

(I) We assume first that \mathbb{K} lies on $s = 2$ parallel lines and show that $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 4k - N - 8$. There is no loss of generality in assuming $d(\mathbb{K}) = \gcd(d_1, d_2) = 1$. Theorem B*, from [S1], pp. 136, gives:

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq (2k - 1) + \min\left(l(K_1) + l(K_2), 2k - 5\right). \tag{4.2}$$

We distinguish two cases: $J = \{1\}$, when $N = k_1$ and $J = \emptyset$, when $N = 0$.

(a) Assume $J = \{1\}$. This means that $l(K_1) < 2k_1 - 2$ and $l(K_2) \geq 2k_2 - 2$. If $l(K_1) + l(K_2) > 2k - 5$, then $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq (2k - 1) + (2k - 5) = 4k - 6$. If $l(K_1) + l(K_2) \leq 2k - 5$, then $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq (2k - 1) + l(K_1) + l(K_2) \geq (2k - 1) + (k_1 - 1) + (2k_2 - 2) = 4k - 4 - k_1$.

(b) Assume $J = \emptyset$. It follows that $l(K_i) \geq 2k_i - 2$, for $1 \leq i \leq 2$. We apply (4.2) and get $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 4k - 6$.

(II) Let $s \geq 3$. Assume that inequality (4.1) holds for all sets of lattice points lying on $2 \leq r < s$ parallel lines and show that (4.1) is true for a set \mathbb{K} lying on s parallel lines. We let $d = d(\mathbb{K})$, $\mathbb{K}^* = \mathbb{K} \setminus K_s$, $d^* = d(\mathbb{K}^*)$ and $\mathbb{K}^{**} = \mathbb{K} \setminus K_1$, $d^{**} = d(\mathbb{K}^{**})$. We have

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + |K_s + K_{s-1}| + |K_s + K_s|. \tag{4.3}$$

In order to use the induction hypothesis for \mathbb{K}^* (or for \mathbb{K}^{**}), we first need to verify if $d(\mathbb{K}) = d(\mathbb{K}^*)$. Therefore, we will consider several cases.

(a) We assume $d^* = d, d_s = d$ and $l(K_s) \leq (2k_s - 3)d$. Then $J(\mathbb{K}^*)$ is included in $J(\mathbb{K})$ and we can apply the induction hypothesis for \mathbb{K}^* . It is enough to show that

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + 4k_s + (k_{s-1} - k_s) - 4. \tag{4.4}$$

Using inequality (4.3), we get $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + (k_{s-1} + k_s - 1) + (2k_s - 1) = |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + 3k_s + k_{s-1} - 2$, which implies (4.4).

(b) We assume $d^* = d, d_s = d$ and $l(K_s) \geq (2k_s - 2)d$. As in case (a), we can apply the induction hypothesis for \mathbb{K}^* and it is enough to prove

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + 5k_s + (k_{s-1} - k_s) - 4. \tag{4.5}$$

We use (4.3) and estimate $|2K_s|$ by Theorem B(i). Thus, $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + (k_{s-1} + k_s - 1) + (3k_s - 3) = |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + 4k_s + k_{s-1} - 4$, which implies (4.5).

(c) We assume $d^* = d$ and $d_s > d$. As in case (a), we can apply the induction hypothesis for \mathbb{K}^* and it is enough to show that

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + 5k_s + (k_{s-1} - k_s) - 4. \tag{4.6}$$

We consider two situations. First, if K_{s-1} intersects $u \geq 2$ different residue classes modulo d_s , i.e. if d_s does not divide d_{s-1} , then we have $K_{s-1} = \bigcup_{1 \leq t \leq u} K_{s-1}^t$ and $|K_s + K_{s-1}| \geq \sum_{1 \leq t \leq u} |K_s + K_{s-1}^t| \geq k_{s-1} + u(k_s - 1) \geq k_{s-1} + 2k_s - 2$. Using (4.3), we get that $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + (k_{s-1} + 2k_s - 2) + (2k_s - 1) = |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + 4k_s + k_{s-1} - 3$, and (4.6) follows. Second, if K_{s-1} lies in exactly one residue class modulo d_s , then d_s divides d_{s-1} and $\gcd(d_{s-1}, d_s) = d_s > d$. Choose $1 \leq j \leq s - 2$ such that

$$\delta = \gcd(d_{j+1}, d_{j+2}, \dots, d_{s-1}, d_s) > d \text{ and } \gcd(d_j, \delta) = d.$$

It follows that in K_j there are at least two elements non-congruent modulo δ . Note that all the sets $K_u + K_v$ with $j + 1 \leq u, v \leq s$ belong to only one residue class modulo δ , and in conclusion $K_j + K_s$ contains at least k_s elements from $(\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}) \setminus (\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*)$; thus

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + k_s + (k_{s-1} + k_s - 1) + (2k_s - 1) = |\mathbb{K}^* + \mathbb{K}^*| + 4k_s + k_{s-1} - 2.$$

It only remains to be shown that inequality (4.1) is true in the following particular case

(d) We assume $d^* > d$ and $d^{**} > d$ and we deduce the following inequality

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - (k_1 + k_s) - 4s. \tag{4.7}$$

First of all, note that $d_s > d$ and $k_1 \geq 2$, by hypothesis $d^{**} > d$. Similarly, $d_1 > d$ and $k_s \geq 2$, in view of $d^* > d$. Since $d^* > d$, it follows that d^* does not divide d_s , which shows that in K_s there are at least two elements non-congruent modulo d^* . Using $d^* = \gcd\{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{s-1}\}$, we get that each of the sets $K_u + K_v$, with $1 \leq u, v \leq s - 1$ is included in only one residue class modulo d^* . We conclude that for every $1 \leq i \leq s - 1$ the set $K_s + K_i$ contains at least k_i elements not belonging to the union

$$\mathbb{U} = 2K_1 \cup \dots \cup 2K_{s-1} \cup (K_1 + K_2) \cup \dots \cup (K_{s-2} + K_{s-1}). \tag{4.8}$$

This means that

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq \sum_{i=1}^{s-2} |2K_i| + \sum_{i=1}^{s-2} |K_i + K_{i+1}| + (k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_{s-2}) + |2(K_s \cup K_{s-1})|. \tag{4.9}$$

As we shall prove later, we have $|2(K_s \cup K_{s-1})| \geq 4k_{s-1} + 3k_s - 4$ and so (4.9) implies that $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - k_1 - 2k_s - 2s + 1$. Unfortunately, this falls short of proving (4.7). Therefore, the argument splits into two cases, depending on how many residue classes modulo d_s the set K_{s-1} intersects.

Case 1: Assume that K_{s-1} does not lie in only one residue class modulo d_s . If $\gcd(d_{s-1}, d_s) = d_s$, then d_s divides d_{s-1} , which contradicts the assumption of this case. If $\gcd(d_{s-1}, d_s) = d_{s-1}$, then d_{s-1} divides d_s and so d^* divides d_s , which contradicts $d^* > d$. In summary, $\gcd(d_{s-1}, d_s) < d_s$ and $\gcd(d_{s-1}, d_s) < d_{s-1}$. Using inequality (4.2), we get $|2(K_s \cup K_{s-1})| \geq 4k_s + 4k_{s-1} - 6$. Applying (4.9), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |2\mathbb{K}| &\geq \sum_{i=1}^{s-2} (2k_i - 1) + \sum_{i=1}^{s-2} (k_i + k_{i+1} - 1) + (k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_{s-2}) + (4k_s + 4k_{s-1} - 6) \\ &= 4k_1 + 5k_2 + \dots + 5k_{s-1} + 4k_s - 2s - 2 = 5k - (k_1 + k_s) - 2s - 2. \end{aligned} \tag{4.10}$$

Case 2: Assume that K_{s-1} is included in only one residue class modulo d_s , i.e. d_s divides d_{s-1} . Since $d_s > d$, it follows that there is an index $j, 1 \leq j \leq s - 2$ such that

- (i) the set K_j contains at least two elements non-congruent modulo d_s .
- (ii) the sets $K_{j+1}, K_{j+2}, \dots, K_{s-1}, K_s$ lie in only one residue class modulo d_s .

Put $D = \gcd(d_s, d^*)$, $d_s = Da$, $d^* = Db$ and note that $\gcd(a, b) = 1, a \geq 2, b \geq 2$. (If $a = 1$, then d_s divides d^* and it follows that d_s divides d , which contradicts $d_s > d$. If $b = 1$, then d^* divides d_s and it follows that d^* divides d , which contradicts $d^* > d$). As we showed in the proof of (4.9), we may write

$$|(K_s + K_i) \setminus \mathbb{U}| \geq k_i, \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq s - 2, \tag{4.11}$$

where \mathbb{U} is defined in (4.8). We claim that the sum $K_s + K_j$ contains at least $k_s + k_j - 1$ elements not belonging to any of the sets

$$2K_i, 1 \leq i \leq s - 1, \tag{4.12}$$

$$K_i + K_{i+1}, 1 \leq i \leq s - 2. \tag{4.13}$$

This follows from Proposition 3, below. Indeed, note first that $K_s + K_j$ intersects at most one of the sets (4.12) and (4.13), say $K_u + K_v$, with $j + 1 \leq u \leq v \leq s - 1$. Using condition (ii), we see that $K_u + K_v$ lies in only one residue class modulo d_s . Moreover, d^* divides d_u and d_v . Consequently, $K_u + K_v$ lies in only one residue class modulo d^* . We deduce that $K_u + K_v$ lies in only one residue

class modulo $\lambda = lcm(d_s, d^*) = Dab$. Note that Da divides $d(K_s) = d_s$ and Db divides $d(K_j) = d_j$. Moreover, K_s contains at least two integers non-congruent modulo Db , (because $Db = d^*$ does not divide d_s) and K_j contains at least two elements non-congruent modulo $Da = d_s$ (in view of (i)). Assertion (ii) of Proposition 3 implies that $|(K_s + K_j) \setminus (K_u + K_v)| \geq k_s + k_j - 1$, and so the claim is established.

We are now able to prove (4.7). We note that $gcd(d_s, d_{s-1}) < d_{s-1}$. (If $gcd(d_s, d_{s-1}) = d_{s-1}$, then d_{s-1} divides d_s and it follows that d^* divides d_s , which contradicts $d^* > d$). Thus, $|K_s + K_{s-1}| \geq k_s + 2k_{s-1} - 2$, in view of Theorem B(ii). Using (4.11), we conclude

$$\begin{aligned}
 |2\mathbb{K}| &\geq \left(\cup_{i=1}^{s-1} |2K_i| \right) \cup \left(\cup_{i=1}^{s-2} |K_i + K_{i+1}| \right) + |K_{s-1} + K_s| + |2K_s| \\
 &\quad + \left[k_1 + \dots + k_{j-1} + (k_s + k_j - 1) + k_{j+1} + \dots + k_{s-2} \right] \\
 &\geq \sum_{i=1}^{s-1} (2k_i - 1) + \sum_{i=1}^{s-2} (k_i + k_{i+1} - 1) + (k_s + 2k_{s-1} - 2) + (2k_s - 1) \\
 &\quad + (k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_{s-2}) + (k_s - 1) = 5k - (k_1 + k_s) - 2s - 1. \tag{4.14}
 \end{aligned}$$

Inequality (4.7) follows from (4.10) and (4.14). The proof of Lemma 3 is complete. □

It remains to state and prove the following result on addition of distinct sets of integers

Proposition 3. *Let a, b and D be integers satisfying $D \geq 1, a > 1, b > 1$ and $gcd(a, b) = 1$. Let U and V be two sets of integers such that $Da|d(U)$ and $Db|d(V)$. Assume that U contains at least two integers non-congruent modulo Db and V contains at least two integers non-congruent modulo Da . Then,*

- (i) $|U + V| \geq 2|U| + 2|V| - 4$,
- (ii) $|(U + V) \setminus \mathcal{P}| \geq |U| + |V| - 1$, for every arithmetic progression \mathcal{P} of difference $\lambda = Dab$.

Proof. It is clear that U and V intersect each at least two residue classes modulo λ , because $\lambda = Dab$ does not divide $d(U)$ or $d(V)$. First of all, split the set U into a union of pairwise disjoint sets $U = U_1 \cup U_2 \cup \dots \cup U_m$, where $m \geq 2$ is the number of distinct residue classes modulo λ , having non-empty intersection with U ; choose $u_i \in U_i$ such that $U_i \subseteq u_i + \lambda\mathbb{Z}$, for every $1 \leq i \leq m$. Further, split the set V into a union of pairwise disjoint sets $V = V_1 \cup V_2 \cup \dots \cup V_n$, where $n \geq 2$ is the number of distinct residue classes modulo λ , having non-empty intersection with V ; choose $v_j \in V_j$ such that $V_j \subseteq v_j + \lambda\mathbb{Z}$, for every $1 \leq j \leq n$. It is obvious that $U + V = \bigcup_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq m \\ 1 \leq j \leq n}} (U_i + V_j)$, and we claim that

$$|U + V| = \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq m \\ 1 \leq j \leq n}} |U_i + V_j|. \tag{4.15}$$

In order to verify (4.15), it is enough to show that U_i+V_j intersects U_k+V_l if and only if $(i, j) = (k, l)$. Indeed, assume that $x \in (U_i + V_j) \cap (U_k + V_l)$ and write

$$x = u'_i + v'_j = u''_k + v''_l, \text{ where} \tag{4.16}$$

$$u'_i \in U_i \subseteq U \text{ and } u''_k \in U_k \subseteq U, \tag{4.17}$$

$$v'_j \in V_j \subseteq V \text{ and } v''_l \in V_l \subseteq V. \tag{4.18}$$

Applying (4.17) and $Da|d(U)$, we deduce that $u'_i \equiv u''_k \pmod{Da}$. This leads to $v'_j \equiv v''_l \pmod{Da}$, as a consequence of (4.16). But $v'_j \equiv v''_l \pmod{Db}$, by (4.18) and hypothesis $Db|d(V)$. We deduce that $v'_j \equiv v''_l \pmod{Dab}$, which shows that $j = l$, due to the definition of the partition $V = V_1 \cup V_2 \cup \dots \cup V_n$. In particular, the last congruence yields

$$u'_i \equiv u''_k \pmod{Dab}, \tag{4.19}$$

as a consequence of equality (4.16). The sets U_i and U_k are included in two distinct residue classes modulo Dab , if we assume $i \neq k$. Thus, the congruence (4.19) leads to equality $i = k$, since $u'_i \in U_i$ and $u''_k \in U_k$. This completes the proof of our claim (4.15).

We now prove assertion (i) of Proposition 3. Using $m, n \geq 2$, and equality (4.15), we get

$$\begin{aligned} |U + V| &= \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq m \\ 1 \leq j \leq n}} |U_i + V_j| \geq \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq m \\ 1 \leq j \leq n}} (|U_i| + |V_j| - 1) \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq i \leq m} (n|U_i| - n + |V|) = n|U| + m|V| - mn \\ &= (n - 2)(|U| - m) + (m - 2)(|V| - n) + (m - 2)(n - 2) + 2|U| + 2|V| - 4 \\ &\geq 2|U| + 2|V| - 4. \end{aligned}$$

We now prove assertion (ii) of Proposition 3. We showed that $U + V$ intersects mn residue classes modulo $\lambda = Dab$. Let \mathcal{P} be an arithmetic progression modulo λ . Without loss of generality, we may assume that \mathcal{P} intersects $U_1 + V_1$. An elementary computation completes the proof:

$$\begin{aligned} |(U + V) \setminus \mathcal{P}| &\geq \sum_{1 \leq i \leq m} (|U_i + V_2| + \dots + |U_i + V_n|) + \sum_{2 \leq i \leq m} |U_i + V_1| \\ &\geq \sum_{1 \leq i \leq m} \left((|U_i| + |V_2| - 1) + \dots + (|U_i| + |V_n| - 1) \right) + \sum_{2 \leq i \leq m} (|U_i| + |V_1| - 1) \\ &\geq \sum_{1 \leq i \leq m} \left((n - 1)(|U_i| - 1) + |V| - |V_1| \right) + \sum_{2 \leq i \leq m} (|U_i| + |V_1| - 1) \\ &= \left((n - 1)(|U| - m) + m(|V| - |V_1|) \right) + \left(|U| - |U_1| + (m - 1)(|V_1| - 1) \right) \\ &= (n|U| + m|V| - mn) - |U_1| - |V_1| + 1 \geq (2|U| + 2|V| - 4) - |U_1| - |V_1| + 1 \\ &\geq (2|U| + 2|V| - 4) - (|U| - 1) - (|V| - 1) + 1 = |U| + |V| - 1. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

5. Covering the Set \mathbb{K} by s Short Intervals.

The next step in the proof is to show that if $|2\mathbb{K}| < \left(\frac{25}{6} - \frac{13}{3(s+1)}\right)k - 4s + 5$, then \mathbb{K} can be covered by s short intervals (see Corollary 2 of Lemma 5). We shall end this section by showing that there is no loss of generality in assuming $d(\mathbb{K}) = 1$ (see Corollary 3 of Lemma 6). We first establish the following simple result, needed in the proof of Lemma 5.

Lemma 4. *Let δ_0 be a positive number. Let \mathbb{W} be a finite set of \mathbb{Z}^2 which lies on $m \geq 2$ parallel lines $(x = x_1), (x = x_2), \dots, (x = x_m)$, where $x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_m$. Suppose that*

- (i) $W_1 = \mathbb{W} \cap (x = x_1) = \{(x_1, y'), (x_1, y'')\}$, with $y'' - y' > 2\delta_0$.
- (ii) For $2 \leq i \leq m$, the set $W_i = \mathbb{W} \cap (x = x_i)$ may be covered by an interval of length δ_0 . Then, $|\mathbb{W} + \mathbb{W}| \geq 5|\mathbb{W}| - (|W_1| + |W_m|) - 2m - 2$.

Proof. As usual, we denote $|W_i|$ by w_i . If $m = 2$, it is obvious that $|\mathbb{W} + \mathbb{W}| = |2W_1| + |W_1 + W_2| + |2W_2| \geq 3 + 2w_2 + (2w_2 - 1) = 4w_2 + 2 = 5|\mathbb{W}| - (w_1 + w_2) - 6$.

Assume $m \geq 3$ and put $W_1 = \{A, B\}$. $\mathbb{W} + \mathbb{W}$ contains at least the following $2m - 1$ disjoint subsets: $2W_1, \dots, 2W_m$ and $W_1 + W_2, \dots, W_{m-1} + W_m$. We claim that each set $W_1 + W_i$, with $3 \leq i \leq m$, contains at least w_i elements not belonging to any of the sets:

$$2W_2, 2W_3, \dots, 2W_m \text{ and } W_2 + W_3, W_3 + W_4, \dots, W_{m-1} + W_m. \tag{5.1}$$

Indeed, the set $W_1 + W_i$ intersects at most one set of the sets (5.1). Moreover, every set $2W_j$ or $W_j + W_{j+1}$, $j \geq 2$, lies in an interval of length $2\delta_0$. Note that $W_1 + W_i = (A + W_i) \cup (B + W_i)$; using the hypothesis (i), it follows that $|(W_1 + W_i) \setminus J| \geq w_i$, for every interval J of length $2\delta_0$. These remarks complete the proof of our claim. We conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{W} + \mathbb{W}| &\geq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq m} |2W_j| + |W_1 + W_2| + \left(\sum_{2 \leq k \leq m-1} |W_k + W_{k+1}| \right) + \sum_{3 \leq i \leq m} |W_i| \\ &\geq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq m} (2w_j - 1) + 2w_2 + \sum_{2 \leq k \leq m-1} (w_k + w_{k+1} - 1) + (|\mathbb{W}| - w_1 - w_2) \\ &= 5|\mathbb{W}| - (w_1 + w_m) - 2m - 2. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

An easy consequence of Lemma 4 is the following lower bound for $|2\mathbb{K}|$.

Lemma 5. *Suppose that there is $1 \leq t \leq s$ and two points $A = (x_t, y') \in \mathbb{K}_t$ and $B = (x_t, y'') \in \mathbb{K}_t$ such that $y'' - y' > (4k_{\max} - 6)d$. Then $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| \geq 5N - 2k_{\max} - 2s + 7$.*

Proof. Define $J = J(\mathbb{K})$ as in Section 4. Let $W_+ = \left(\bigcup_{\substack{j \in J \\ j > t}} \mathbb{K}_j\right) \cup \{A, B\}$ and $W_- = \left(\bigcup_{\substack{j \in J \\ j < t}} \mathbb{K}_j\right) \cup \{A, B\}$. It is clear that the set W_+ lies on $m_+ = |\{j \in J : j > t\}| + 1$ parallel lines and W_- lies

on $m_- = |\{j \in J : j < t\}| + 1$ parallel lines. Note that for every $j \in J$, the set \mathbb{K}_j can be covered by one interval of length smaller than $(2k_{\max} - 3)d$. The sets W_+ and W_- satisfy the hypothesis of Lemma 4, with $\delta_0 = (2k_{\max} - 3)d$ and $W_1 = \{A, B\}$. We complete the proof of Lemma 5 by examining two simple cases:

Case i. Assume that $W_- = \{A, B\}$ (the case $W_+ = \{A, B\}$ is similar). Using Lemma 4 for $\mathbb{W} = W_+$ we get:

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| &\geq |W_+ + W_+| \geq 5|W_+| - (2 + k_{\max}) - 2m_+ - 2 = 5(N + 2) - k_{\max} - 2m_+ - 4 \\ &\geq 5N + 10 - k_{\max} - 2s - 4 = 5N - k_{\max} - 2s + 6. \end{aligned}$$

Case ii. If $m_- \geq 2$ and $m_+ \geq 2$ we apply Lemma 4 twice, for W_+ and W_- . We get

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| &\geq |W_+ + W_+| + |W_- + W_-| - 3 \\ &\geq \left(5|W_+| - k_{\max} - 2m_+ - 4\right) + \left(5|W_-| - k_{\max} - 2m_- - 4\right) - 3 \\ &= 5(|W_+| + |W_-|) - 2k_{\max} - 2(m_+ + m_-) - 11 \\ &= 5(N + 4) - 2k_{\max} - 2(m_+ + m_-) - 11 = 5N - 2k_{\max} - 2s + 7. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2. *If $|2\mathbb{K}| < \left(\frac{25}{6} - \frac{13}{3(s+1)}\right)k - 4s + 5$, then each set \mathbb{K}_i , $1 \leq i \leq s$, can be covered by an interval of length $(4k_{\max} - 6)d(\mathbb{K})$.*

Proof. Assume that there is an integer t , $1 \leq t \leq s$, such that the set \mathbb{K}_t cannot be covered by an interval of length $(4k_{\max} - 6)d(\mathbb{K})$. By Lemma 5, we get that $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5N - 2k_{\max} - 2s + 7$. Adding this inequality to inequality (4.1) multiplied by 5, we get $6|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 25k - 12k_{\max} - 22s + 7$. This implies $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq \frac{25}{6}k - 2k_{\max} - 4s + 1$. Recall that $k_{\max} \leq \frac{1}{s-1}(|2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + s)$, by Lemma 1 (ii); it follows that $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq \frac{25}{6}k - \frac{2}{s-1}(|2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + s) - 4s + 1$; we get $\frac{s+1}{s-1}|2\mathbb{K}| \geq \left(\frac{25}{6} + \frac{4}{s-1}\right)k - \frac{2s}{s-1} - 4s + 1$, which contradicts the small doubling hypothesis assumed in Corollary 2. \square

The following Lemma shows that if $|2\mathbb{K}| < 5k - 3k_{\max} - 2s$, then, without loss of generality, we can restrict ourselves to the case when $d = d(\mathbb{K}) = 1$. In order to formulate it, we need the following notation: for $1 \leq i \leq s - 1$ we denote by \mathcal{L}_i the set

$$\mathcal{L}_i = \mathbf{P}_i + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{a}_i + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{d} = \{\mathbf{P}_i + \alpha\mathbf{a}_i + \beta\mathbf{d}; \alpha \in \mathbb{Z}, \beta \in \mathbb{Z}\},$$

where $\mathbf{P}_i = (x_i, m_i)$, $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{P}_{i+1} - \mathbf{P}_i = (x_{i+1}, m_{i+1}) - (x_i, m_i)$ and $\mathbf{d} = d\mathbf{e}_2 = (0, d(\mathbb{K}))$.

Lemma 6. *Suppose that the set $\mathbb{K} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^2$ lies on $s \geq 3$ parallel lines. Then either*

(i) $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - 3k_{\max} - 2s$, or

(ii) there is $1 \leq u \leq s - 1$, such that \mathbb{K} is included in $\mathcal{L}_u = \mathbf{P}_u + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{a}_u + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{d}$.

Proof. If $\mathbb{K} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_1$, then assertion (ii) holds with $u = 1$. Thus, there is no loss of generality in assuming that

$$\text{the set } \mathbb{K} \text{ is not included in } \mathcal{L}_1. \tag{5.2}$$

I. We show that the removal of \mathbb{K}_1 from \mathbb{K} reduces the cardinality of $\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}$ by at least $5k_1 + (k_2 - k_1) - 2$. More precisely, we shall prove that

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k_1 + (k_2 - k_1) - 2 + |2(\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{K}_1)|. \tag{5.3}$$

In view of assumption (5.2), we can choose t , $2 \leq t \leq s - 1$ the largest integer such that $\mathbb{K}_i \subseteq \mathcal{L}_1$, for every $1 \leq i \leq t$. It follows that the set \mathbb{K}_{t+1} contains at least one point not in \mathcal{L}_1 . Moreover, in view of $d = d(\mathbb{K})$ divides $d_{t+1} = d(\mathbb{K}_{t+1})$, it is clear that $\mathbb{K}_{t+1} \cap \mathcal{L}_1 = \emptyset$. As one can easily check $\mathbb{K}_1 + \mathbb{K}_{t+1}$ does not intersect $2(\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{K}_1)$ and thus

$$\begin{aligned} |2\mathbb{K}| &\geq |2\mathbb{K}_1| + |\mathbb{K}_1 + \mathbb{K}_2| + |\mathbb{K}_1 + \mathbb{K}_{t+1}| + |2(\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{K}_1)| \\ &\geq (2k_1 - 1) + (k_1 + k_2 - 1) + (k_1 + k_{t+1} - 1) + |2(\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{K}_1)| \geq 4k_1 + k_2 - 2 + |2(\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{K}_1)|. \end{aligned}$$

Assertion (I) is now proved. For every $1 \leq j \leq s$, we let $\mathbb{K}^{(j)}$ denote $\mathbb{K}_j \cup \mathbb{K}_{j+1} \cup \dots \cup \mathbb{K}_s$. By inequality (5.3), we can choose $2 \leq u \leq s$ the largest integer such that

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5(k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_{i-1}) + (k_i - k_1) - 2i + 2 + |2\mathbb{K}^{(i)}|, \text{ for every } 2 \leq i \leq u. \tag{5.4}$$

There is no loss of generality in assuming $u \leq s - 1$. Indeed, if $u = s$, then (5.4) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} |2\mathbb{K}| &\geq 5(k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_{s-1}) + (k_s - k_1) - 2s + 2 + |2\mathbb{K}^{(s)}| \\ &\geq 5(k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_{s-1}) + (k_s - k_1) - 2s + 2 + (2k_s - 1) \\ &= 5k - k_1 - 2k_s - 2s + 1 \geq 5k - 3k_{\max} - 2s + 1 \end{aligned}$$

and so (i) is established.

II. We prove that $\mathbb{K}^{(u)}$ is included in \mathcal{L}_u . To the contrary, choose v the smallest integer $u + 2 \leq v \leq s$, such that \mathbb{K}_v is not included in \mathcal{L}_u . It is clear that $\mathbb{K}_u + \mathbb{K}_v$ does not intersect any of the sets $\mathbb{K}_i + \mathbb{K}_j$, with $u + 1 \leq i, j \leq v - 1$. Therefore,

$$|2\mathbb{K}^{(u)}| \geq |2\mathbb{K}_u| + |\mathbb{K}_u + \mathbb{K}_{u+1}| + |\mathbb{K}_u + \mathbb{K}_v| + |2\mathbb{K}^{(u+1)}| \geq (4k_u + k_{u+1} + k_v - 3) + |2\mathbb{K}^{(u+1)}|.$$

In view of (5.4), this implies the following lower bound

$$\begin{aligned} |2\mathbb{K}| &\geq 5(k_1 + \dots + k_{u-1}) + (k_u - k_1) - 2u + 2 + |2\mathbb{K}^{(u)}| \\ &\geq 5(k_1 + \dots + k_{u-1}) + (k_u - k_1) - 2u + 2 + (4k_u + k_{u+1} + k_v - 3) + |2\mathbb{K}^{(u+1)}| \\ &\geq 5(k_1 + \dots + k_u) + (k_{u+1} - k_1) - 2(u + 1) + 2 + |2\mathbb{K}^{(u+1)}|, \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts the maximal property of u .

The last step of the proof is

III. We prove that if the set \mathbb{K} is not included in \mathcal{L}_u , then $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - 3k_{\max} - 2s$. Note that $u \geq 2$, in view of (II) and (5.2). Choose the biggest integer $1 \leq v \leq u - 1$, such that the set \mathbb{K}_v is not included in \mathcal{L}_u . In the special case of $v = 1$, the sets $\mathbb{K}_2, \dots, \mathbb{K}_s$ are included in \mathcal{L}_u and \mathbb{K}_1 is not included in \mathcal{L}_u ; thus, we may use inequality (2.7) for the set \mathbb{K} from which we deduce $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - (k_1 + k_2 + k_s) - 2s \geq 5k - 3k_{\max} - 2s$.

Finally, we assume $v \geq 2$. In view of (5.4) we obtain

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5(k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_{v-1}) + (k_v - k_1) - 2v + 2 + |2\mathbb{K}^{(v)}|. \tag{5.5}$$

On the one hand, $\mathbb{K}^{(v+1)} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_u$; on the other hand, \mathbb{K}_v is not included in \mathcal{L}_u . Applying inequality (2.7) once again, this time for the set $\mathbb{K}^{(v)}$, we deduce

$$|2\mathbb{K}^{(v)}| \geq 5(k_v + \dots + k_s) - (k_v + k_{v+1} + k_s) - 2(s - v + 1). \tag{5.6}$$

Combining (5.5) and (5.6) we obtain the desired result $|2\mathbb{K}| \geq 5k - (k_1 + k_{v+1} + k_s) - 2s \geq 5k - 3k_{\max} - 2s$. The proof of Lemma 6 is now complete. \square

Corollary 3. Assume that $d(X) = 1, \mathbf{P}_1 = (0, 0) \in \mathbb{K}$ and

$$|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| < 5|\mathbb{K}| - 3k_{\max} - 2s. \tag{5.7}$$

Then, there is an integer t such that $m_i = \min(K_i) \equiv tx_i \pmod{d(\mathbb{K})}$, for every $1 \leq i \leq s$.

Proof. By Lemma 6, there is $1 \leq u \leq s - 1$ such that $\mathbb{K} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_u = \mathbf{P}_u + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{a}_u + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{d}$, with $\mathbf{d} = (0, d(\mathbb{K}))$. Note that $\mathbf{P}_1 = (0, 0) \in \mathbb{K} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_u$, implies that $\mathbf{P}_u \in \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{a}_u + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{d}$ and thus

$$\mathbb{K} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_u = \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{a}_u + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{d}.$$

Recalling that $\mathbf{a}_u = \mathbf{P}_{u+1} - \mathbf{P}_u = (x_{u+1}, m_{u+1}) - (x_u, m_u)$, and using $\mathbf{P}_i \in \mathbb{K} \cap \mathcal{L}_u$, we deduce there exist integers α_i and β_i such that

$$\mathbf{P}_i = (x_i, m_i) = \alpha_i \mathbf{a}_u + \beta_i \mathbf{d} = \alpha_i (x_{u+1} - x_u, m_{u+1} - m_u) + \beta_i (0, d), \text{ for every } 1 \leq i \leq s.$$

Since $d(X) = \gcd(x_2 - x_1, \dots, x_s - x_1) = 1$ and $x_1 = 0$, it follows that $x_{u+1} - x_u = 1$ and consequently $\alpha_i = x_i$. Moreover, if we let $t = m_{u+1} - m_u$, then

$$m_i = \alpha_i (m_{u+1} - m_u) + \beta_i d = x_i t + \beta_i d \equiv tx_i \pmod{d(\mathbb{K})},$$

for every $1 \leq i \leq s$. Corollary 3 is proved. \square

6. Proof of Theorem 1.

Let us put together the results obtained so far. Recall that for every $1 \leq i \leq s$ the set \mathbb{K}_i lies on the line $(x = x_i)$, K_i denotes the set of ordinates of \mathbb{K}_i and $m_i = \min(K_i)$. Assume that $d(X) = 1, \mathbf{P}_1 = (0, 0)$ and

$$|2\mathbb{K}| < \left(4 + \varepsilon - \frac{4(1 + \varepsilon)}{s + 1}\right)|\mathbb{K}| - 4s + 3. \tag{6.1}$$

Corollary 1 and inequality (ii) of Lemma 1 yield the estimates

$$l(X) = x_s - x_1 = x_s \leq 2s - 3, \tag{6.2}$$

$$k_{\max} \leq \frac{1}{s - 1}(|2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + s) < \frac{1}{s - 1}\left(2 + \varepsilon - \frac{4(1 + \varepsilon)}{s + 1}\right)k. \tag{6.3}$$

Using the small doubling hypothesis (6.1) and inequality (6.3), we deduce that $|2\mathbb{K}| < 5k - 3k_{\max} - 2s$ and so we can apply the result of Corollary 3. Consequently, the set \mathbb{K} is included in the lattice $\mathcal{L} = \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{a} + \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{d}$, with $\mathbf{a} = (1, t) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and $\mathbf{d} = (0, d(\mathbb{K}))$. After a coordinate change $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{e}_1$ and $\mathbf{d} \rightarrow \mathbf{e}_2$, we may assume that

$$d = d(\mathbb{K}) = \gcd(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_s) = 1.$$

Since (6.1) implies $|2\mathbb{K}| < \left(\frac{25}{6} - \frac{13}{3(s+1)}\right)k - 4s + 5$, we can use Corollary 2. We conclude that if (6.1) is true, then \mathbb{K} is contained in $2s - 2$ equidistant parallel arithmetic progressions (because of (6.2)) and each set $\mathbb{K}_i, 1 \leq i \leq s$, is included in a short arithmetic progression

$$\{\mathbf{P}_i, \mathbf{P}_i + \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{P}_i + l_i\mathbf{e}_2\}. \tag{6.4}$$

of length $l_i = M_i - m_i = \max K_i - \min K_i \leq 4k_{\max} - 6$. In order to complete the proof of Theorem 1, we need to show that the points $\mathbf{P}_1, \mathbf{P}_2, \dots, \mathbf{P}_s$ are "almost" collinear. We are able to prove this, only if we replace (6.1) by the small doubling hypothesis (1.1).

Lemma 7. *Let ℓ_0 be a positive integer. Suppose that each set $\mathbb{K}_i, 1 \leq i \leq s$, is contained in an arithmetic progression $\{\mathbf{P}_i, \mathbf{P}_i + \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{P}_i + \ell_0\mathbf{e}_2\}$. If $|\mathbb{K} + \mathbb{K}| < \left(4 - \frac{2}{s+1}\right)|\mathbb{K}| - (2s + 1)$ and $s \geq 19$, then \mathbb{K} lies inside the parallelogram \mathcal{P} defined by the vertices $v_1 = \mathbf{P}_1 - \ell_0\mathbf{e}_2, v_2 = \mathbf{P}_s - \ell_0\mathbf{e}_2, v_3 = \mathbf{P}_1 + 2\ell_0\mathbf{e}_2$ and $v_4 = \mathbf{P}_s + 2\ell_0\mathbf{e}_2$.*

Proof. Note that (2.1) and (1.1) imply that

$$k_1 + k_s \geq (4k - |2\mathbb{K}|) - (2s - 1) > \frac{2}{s + 1}k + 2. \tag{6.5}$$

Without loss of generality we may assume that $\mathbf{P}_1 = (0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{P}_s = (x_s, 0)$.

We next show that the cardinality of the set $\mathbb{L} = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{K} : 0 \leq y < \ell_0\}$, which includes $\mathbb{K}_1 \cup \mathbb{K}_s$, is almost equal to k . Choose $\mathbf{P} = (x_P, M) \in \mathbb{K}$ and $\mathbf{p} = (x_p, m) \in \mathbb{K}$ such that for every $(x, y) \in \mathbb{K}$ we have $m \leq y \leq M$. Let $\mathbb{L}_+ = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{K}, y \geq \ell_0\}$, $\mathbb{L}_- = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{K}, y < 0\}$. On the one hand, for every $1 \leq j \leq s$ we have

$$\mathbb{K}_1 + \mathbb{K}_j \subseteq (m \leq y < M + \ell_0) \text{ and } \mathbb{K}_j + \mathbb{K}_s \subseteq (m \leq y < M + \ell_0);$$

on the other hand, $\mathbf{P} + \mathbb{L}_+ \subseteq (y \geq M + \ell_0)$ and $\mathbf{p} + \mathbb{L}_- \subseteq (y < m)$. An elementary computation and inequality (6.5) give

$$\begin{aligned} |2\mathbb{K}| &\geq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq s} |\mathbb{K}_1 + \mathbb{K}_j| + \sum_{2 \leq j \leq s} |\mathbb{K}_j + \mathbb{K}_s| + |\mathbf{P} + \mathbb{L}_+| + |\mathbf{p} + \mathbb{L}_-| \\ &\geq 2k + (s - 1)(k_1 + k_s) - (2s - 1) + |\mathbb{L}_+| + |\mathbb{L}_-| \geq \\ &\geq 2k + (s - 1)(k_1 + k_s) - (2s - 1) + (|\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{L}|) \\ &\geq 3k + (s - 1)[4k - |2\mathbb{K}| - (2s - 1)] - (2s - 1) - |\mathbb{L}|. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $|\mathbb{L}| \geq (4s - 1)k - s|2\mathbb{K}| - (s - 1)(2s - 1) - (2s - 1) = k - s \left[|2\mathbb{K}| - \left(4 - \frac{2}{s}\right)k + (2s - 1) \right] > k - \left(\frac{2}{s+1}k - 2s\right)$. To summarize

$$|\mathbb{L}| = |\mathbb{K} \cap (0 \leq y < \ell_0)| \geq \frac{s - 1}{s + 1}k + 2s. \tag{6.6}$$

Note that $|\mathbb{L}| \geq 11$, $\dim \mathbb{L} = 2$ and the set \mathbb{L} does not lie on two parallel lines. In view of Theorem A(ii), we get that $|2\mathbb{L}| \geq \frac{10}{3}|\mathbb{L}| - 5$. In order to prove Lemma 6, it will be enough to show that \mathbb{K} lies between the lines $(y = -\ell_0)$ and $(y = 2\ell_0)$. To the contrary, assume that there is a point $\mathbf{R} = (x_r, y_r) \in \mathbb{K}$ such that $y_r > 2\ell_0$ or $y_r < -\ell_0$. Then, $\mathbf{R} + \mathbb{L}$ does not intersect the set $2\mathbb{L}$ and thus

$$|2\mathbb{K}| \geq |2\mathbb{L}| + |\mathbf{R} + \mathbb{L}| \geq \frac{10}{3}|\mathbb{L}| - 5 + |\mathbb{L}| = \frac{13}{3}|\mathbb{L}| - 5 \geq \frac{13}{3}\left(\frac{s - 1}{s + 1}k + 2s\right) - 5,$$

which contradicts (1.1), for $s \geq 19$. Lemma 7 is proved. □

We conclude the proof of Theorem 1 by using Lemma 7, with $\ell_0 = 4k_{\max} - 6$; we get

$$|\mathcal{P} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2| \leq (2s - 2)(3\ell_0 + 1) \leq 2(s - 1)(12k_{\max} - 17) \leq 24(s - 1)(k_{\max} - 1) \leq 24(|2\mathbb{K}| - 2k + 1),$$

in view of Lemma 1(ii). Theorem 1 is proved. □

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